

Eurodoc's Gender Equality, Equality, and Anti Discrimination Plan (GEP)

Introduction

Eurodoc's vision is that of “a fair and sustainable research culture where early career researchers are treated with respect and have access to long-term and stable career pathways”, and its mission is that of advocating “for positive change in the policies, culture and environment that affect the quality of training, well-being and employment conditions of early career researchers”. Thus, working towards more equitable opportunities is a core part of the work Eurodoc does.

Eurodoc has always had the people and their perspectives at its core, and this is where its strength as an advocate stems from. For most Eurodoc volunteers, the “Eurodocers”, our organisation has been a place where one could find moral support in the difficulties of the PhD journey, mutual help in the development of tasks, fair collaboration for the achievement of common goals, and personal career development opportunities. The Eurodoc culture was set from the beginning on mutual respect and mutual valorisation of each other's capabilities, skills, and aspirations.

This document, Eurodoc's Gender Equality, Equality, and Anti Discrimination Plan (GEP) initiated by the 2021/2022 Board, should be seen as following this tradition. The first iteration of the GEP was approved by the Annual General Meeting in 2023. This GEP is a living document and should be regularly updated. The second iteration of the GEP was approved by the Annual General Meeting in 2025.

Eurodoc's organisational culture in terms of equality and equity

The following four pillars have been identified as crucial on the basis of the Toolkit “Gender Equality in Academia” developed by the European Institution for Gender Equality¹ and to ensure the continuation of the traditional open and welcoming organisational culture of Eurodoc, which is the foundation of the organisational culture we want to strengthen inside and outside Eurodoc:

- Gender distribution of elected positions
- Recruitment processes of volunteers and recognition of volunteers' contributions
- Work-life balance
- Measures towards preventing gender based violence

On this basis, we aim to adopt the GEP methodology to tackle other forms of discrimination as well.

¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

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Gender distribution of elected positions

In the recent past Eurodoc has had a good gender balance with a slight majority of women in elected positions. In the last years, its boards have usually consisted of more women than men.² The same is true for the Secretariat—however: That the positions which traditionally receive less recognition are conducted by a majority of women needs careful attention.³ It is very important that the board ensures that these positions receive the acknowledgement for the work they conduct on behalf of Eurodoc.

Recruitment procedures and recognition of volunteers' contributions

Positions in the board require an affiliation with a National Association (NAs), but other positions do not have this requirement. Eurodoc Working Groups (WGs) are open to any early career researcher, and support individuals to get in touch with NA members of Eurodoc. Similarly, the Eurodoc administration actively invites NAs to encourage their members to join Eurodoc activities and to run for elected positions.

In encouraging individuals to step up for positions, the Eurodoc administration highlights the importance of an open and welcoming organisational culture. Volunteers have the chance to take on responsibility and leadership roles in a supportive environment, developing transferable skills that will strengthen their career development opportunities. Eurodoc is able to encourage e.g. women and people who experience(d) marginalisation to be included in our team.

At the same time, for Eurodoc to continue to perform this task with full awareness, it is necessary that Eurodocers are openly recognized for their contributions. "Credit where credit is due" is an important component of Open Science, and how to recognize these contributions has been a focus of Eurodoc for several years. Eurodoc maintains clear procedures for authorship and other contributions, as well as a standard of issuing diplomas for participation in conferences, presentations, and for serving in elected positions. These practices are written into Eurodoc's code of conduct.

Work-life balance

A domain where Eurodoc potentially can have large shortcomings is that of ensuring work-life balance. In general, ECRs' worklife is pervaded by a narrative that praises overworking, and volunteer activity can sometimes implicate an attitude of self-sacrifice. Since Eurodocers contribute on a voluntary basis—often on top of already precarious and demanding academic work—this can further strain their well-being and work-life balance, with potential consequences for their physical and mental health.

²The 2020-2021 Board 3 men and 4 women, the 2021-2022 Board 2 men and 5 women, the 2022-2023 Board 3 men and 4 women, the 2023-2024 Board 2 men and 4 women, the 2024-2025 board 3 men and 4 women. Data is available on the Eurodoc website.

³ The 2020-2021 Secretariat 6 men and 18 women, the 2021-2022 Secretariat 7 men and 12 women, the 2022-2023 Secretariat 4 men and 12 women, the 2023-2024 3 men and 9 women, the 2024-2025 Secretariat men 4 and 9 women. Data is available on the Eurodoc website.

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Gender-based violence

Reducing gender-based violence is an important topic and identifying measures to prevent such is a crucial part of a GEP. To this, we want to add our commitment to prevent violent behaviours against any person, including those coming from marginalised categories.

Eurodoc strives to provide a safe environment where any type of gender-based violence, including sexual violence or harassment, is unacceptable, whether it happens at internal Eurodoc meetings or at external meetings representing Eurodoc. We believe that Eurodoc can strengthen its ability to recognise and prevent gender-based violence and violence against marginalised groups through training material, available to all individuals in Eurodoc and for NAs.

Eurodoc's commitments for 2025-2027

The key commitment to developing a Eurodoc Code of Conduct has been fulfilled in 2025. In a next step, Eurodoc commits itself for period 2025-2027 to take the following actions:

- To evaluate the implementation of Eurodoc's Code of Conduct. *The work should be led by the Administrative Board of Eurodoc.*
- To collect open educational resources on the topic of equitable opportunities. *This work should be led by a working group.*

As mandated by the GEP basic requirements, these measures will be iteratively evaluated and reviewed with a regular participatory process every second term. On this basis, a new analysis and a new round of concrete measures will be presented to the 2027 AGM for approval.

Approved by the Annual General Meeting 2025

Date of Publication of Second Action Plan: 09.08.2025

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early career researchers (ECRs) from 24 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established in 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

